

Management

SAFETY AND SECURITY MEASURES ADOPTED BY THE HOTELS AND THEIR IMPACT ON CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Hotel can be defined as “Home away from home” for the guests who come to the hotel as they receive homely environment and services in the hotel. The guests who come to the hotels come with an understanding that they and their belongings would be safe and secured in the hotel during their occupancy in the hotel. The safety and security aspects play a very vital role in hospitality industry as this industry is dependent largely on the customer relationship with the hotel. If the guest encounters any security issue during their stay in the hotel, it leads to dissatisfaction of the guests resulting in Cognitive dissonance due to which the guests seeks other hotels and their buying consumer behavior becomes variety seeking consumer behavior. On the other hand, if the guests face no security and safety issue during their stay in the hotel, it leads to guest satisfaction resulting in improvement of rapport and good will of the hotel in the society thereby achieving its main objectives of PROFIT MAXIMIZATION AND GUEST SATISFACTION.

Keywords: Customer Relationship; Cognitive Dissonance; Variety Seeking Consumer Behavior; Rapport; Profit Maximization; Guest Satisfaction.

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1. Introduction

The aim of the safety and security measures followed by the hotels is to reduce the crime, terrorism, natural disasters and from any man made hazards. The hotel security covers various aspects like guest room locking, public area security and security of the system with equipment's found in the hotel. To maintain an effective safety and security plan, the Front Office Department should have a regular and continuous co-ordination with the security department of the Hotel which results in pleasant stay of the guest exceeding the expectations thereby fostering the Customer Relationship Management. A hotel always strives to maintain healthy and positive guest relations to improve their business and to generate maximum revenue every time which is

only possible if the guest has a pleasant stay in the hotel without having any issues or complaints related to their stay in the hotel.

So, the safety and the security measures adopted by the hotels should be efficient enough and updated so that the guests encounters minimum or no damage to themselves and their belongings in the case of even slightest safety issue.

2. Objectives

- To find out the importance of Safety & Security measures used in the Hotels and its impact on CRM.
- To analyze the various Safety & Security measures performance in the hotel.
- To find out the various emergency situations in the hotels and their handling procedure.
- To find out the relationship between safety & security measures and guest relations.

3. Customer Relationship Management

Customer Relationship management can be defined in different ways

It also means different things to different people depending on the working environment it have been used in Therefore there is no single definition of Customer Relationship Management (Brown, 2000).

The CRM helps the hospitality firms to customize the products and services according to the customer's expectations in return of which the perceived value gets improved. The perceived value is calculated with the perceived quality by customers, leading to enhancement of customer delight and satisfaction.

Alignment of incentives and metrics, deployment of knowledge management systems, tracking customer defection and retention levels and customer service satisfaction levels are other contributions of CRM Technology. (Mehta, 2010)

Customer relationship management (CRM) is a strategy that can help them to build long lasting relationships with their customers and increase their profits through the right management system and the application of customer focused strategies. (Parvatiyar, 2001)

It is very correctly said that HOTEL is "HOME AWAY FROM HOME" for the guests, so the guests want to receive no or minimum dissatisfaction during their stay in the hotels.

It is a vital duty of the management of the hotel to ensure that the guests receive no external or internal threats in the hotel resulting in comfortable and pleasant stay for the guests. The hotels should use various types of security measures for the guests especially the female guests as they are considered to be an easy target for the intruders.

In the recent time, there have been many havoc incidents of terrorism, fire, bomb explosion and even vandalism in India which has made the Indian hotel industry to be vigilant enough to face any sort of emergency situations. Besides that the Indian hotel industry has started adopting

security measures and even physical security measures like Scanning and Frisking to ensure no dissatisfaction for the guests during their length of stay in the hotels.

4. Hospitality Industry and the CRM

The hospitality industry is a service sector which largely depends on the relationship of the hotels with its customers. This industry is mainly dependent on relationship marketing. Many hospitality organizations have failed to understand what really the needs and requirements of the customers are which makes them fail to provide perfect service delivery. Many other hotels understand the needs and requirements of the customers but were unable to transform the expectations of the customers into their delight or satisfaction. The Customer Relationship Management is a technique or a business strategy to select the most valuable customer relationship. In the hospitality industry, there are different types of guests broadly classified as business class and leisure each of which have their different needs and requirements. The hospitality industry should try to maintain the loyalty and patronage of their customers to get the competitive advantage over other hospitality providers in the market. The hospitality organizations should try to provide lucrative offers and packages to their repeat guests as well as the first time guests to effectively maintain prosperous and fostered relations with their customers.

The hospitality organizations should even try to investigate the buying patterns and their post sales experience of the customers. If the service delivery process(output) matches or is above the expectations of the guests, then the guests becomes loyal for the hotel and even starts word of mouth marketing of the hotel in a positive sense. If the service delivery process (output) does not match or is below the expectations of the guests, it leads to customer dissonance and the customers seek for other available hotels in the market.

The customers' needs are ever-changing and for that, the hospitality organizations should be geared up and ready all the times. To implement and adopt CRM in the hospitality organizations, it is important that all the levels of management get involved into it and it should not be confined to just one customer but to all the customers who come and stay in the hotels may be they are repeat or the first time guests.

5. Types of Security in the Hotels

Security mainly covers following three aspects

- 1) PHYSICAL ASPECT OF SECURITY
- 2) SECURITY OF THE PEOPLE
- 3) SECURITY OF SYSTEMS AND MACHINERIES

5.1. Physical Aspect of Security

It mainly covers the internal and external security of the guests and the staff of the hotel. The internal security covers security issues against theft, proper lightning, fire safety and even tracking the unwanted guests in the hotels. The external security aspect covers issues to

minimize the incidents inside and outside the premises of the hotel. The external security measures used are proper manning of security guards in the hotel, proper fencing of the pool area and even the installation of CCTV (Closed circuit television) cameras within the campus of the hotel.

5.2. Security of the People

The security of the people encompasses security of hotel staff and the most important security of the guests. Out of these, the security of guests is of prime importance as it can affect the business and operations of the hotel. For security of staff measures like effective recruitment /selection, identification of staff, checking previous records of the staff with previous employers etc should be adopted. For the security of the guests, there should be efficient guests room security, wide angle door viewer, night torches, chain on doors etc. Even the hotel staff should be briefed not to reveal any confidential or any sort of information of the in-house guests to the outsiders.

5.3. Security of the Systems and Machineries

In hotels, there are very expensive equipments which are used during daily operations. All the records of missing or misplaced items should be made and regular physical inventory should be done to check the missing or misplaced items. The main system room should be locked always when not in use to avoid the important information to be accessed by the unwanted people.

6. Types of Emergency Situations Encountered in Hotels

During the operations and functioning of the hotel, there can be any emergency situation which can come across. The hotel staff should be well trained to find an optimum, quick and proactive solution to these emergencies. The various types of emergency situations encountered in hotels are as under:-

- 1) BOMB THREAT EMERGENCY SITUATION
- 2) FIRE THREAT EMERGENCY SITUATION
- 3) DEATH OF AN IN-HOUSE GUESTS IN THE HOTEL
- 4) ACCIDENT EMERGENCY SITUATION
- 5) THEFT EMERGENCY SITUATION
- 6) ILLNESS AND EPIDEMICS EMERGENCY SITUATION
- 7) HANDLING DRUNKEN GUEST

6.1. Bomb Threat Emergency Situation

In case of any call received regarding the bomb threat, the hotel should tie up with the local police authority and follow their instructions. The person who receives the call should take complete details of the situation and should even try to note down the voice and accent of the person calling regarding a bomb threat. Immediately the hotel should inform the anti bomb squad and should defuse the bomb after locating the place where it is planted.

6.2. Fire Threat Emergency Situation

Fire is the most common emergency situation which could break in the hotel at any point of time. The most probable reason of fire break in the hotels can be kitchen or faulty wirings in the hotel. The concerned staff should be immediately informed and fire brigade should be informed immediately. Do not panic. If the hotel staff is well versed with the fire fighting equipments then immediately fire extinguisher should be used. The supply of electricity and gas should be immediately turned off whenever any news regarding fire comes to the hotel.

6.3. Death of an In-House Guest in the Hotel

Whenever information comes regarding death of an in-house guest the Front Office Manager should be reported directly who informs the General Manager and the Security Manager. Later on the police authority is even told and the hotel doctor is summoned to confirm the death of the guest. The residential address of the guests is also identified and the relatives are informed. Once the doctor has confirmed the death and the police has given the permission the dead body is removed by the help of a stretcher. In the meanwhile if the deceased guest was under some other doctor consultation then that doctor is also enquired. A death certificate is also prepared and a report is prepared mentioning the time, room number and other details related to the deceased guest. The guest room is locked and sealed and after the permission and clearance of police the room is opened and spring cleaned and can be resold again after the approval of the local authority.

6.4. Accident Emergency Situation

Accidents can take place in the hotels at any point of time due to faulty stairs, ramps, balconies and even due to the parking places. The hotels should ensure that handrails, non slip surface should be used while framing the architecture plan for the hotels.

6.5. Theft Emergency Situation

Front desk is having cash with them so there is also possibility of theft. Also there are belongings of in house guest .To discourage theft, front office should inform the guest to deposit their valuables in the safety deposit locker.

6.6. Illness and Epidemics Emergency Situation

There should always be a Doctor on call available for the hotel so that in case if any guest suffers from any kind of problem he /she can be given the concern treatment as soon as possible.

6.7. Handling Drunken Guest

A drunken guest may disturb other guest. In order to avoid this the drunken guest should be escorted to an isolated area like back office. Hotel staff should calmly handle the situation.

7. Security Measures Adopted By the Hotels

In order to make the guests stay a pleasant and memorable experience, the hotels adopt certain security measures like

7.1. Key Card Locks

There should be an efficient key card locking system (Electronic Locking System) which should be directly interfaced with the Property Management System of the hotel so that guest room access can be supervised.

7.2. Security Guards

All the hotels should have well trained security personnel not only during the night time but even during the day time and they should be well versed to deal with any sort of emergency situations. Even the security guards should be well trained with the firefighting equipments. Besides all the above security measures, there should be a check on external, internal, material and people access control. They should try to anticipate movements of each and every guest whether in-house or an outside visitor to the hotel.

7.3. Defibrillation Units

Defibrillation units should be deployed among police and all the emergency communication managers in the hotel to sought out any incident of heart attacks etc. in the hotel.

7.4. Security Cameras / Cctv Cameras

There should be adequate provisions of security cameras / CCTV cameras with digital technology and intelligent access central system in the hotel to check the external and internal premises of the hotel. These cameras should be linked up with the Property management system of the hotel. Even a link is required between cameras and motion detectors, biometric readers like hand key reader or face recognition system etc.

7.5. Fire Alarms

Fire now a day has become a very common emergency situation in the hotels. To deal with the emergency of fire, hotels should install smoke detectors and fire alarms in each guest room and corridors to monitor entire complex round the clock. The hotel staff should be well trained with the firefighting equipments and should be told practically on how to use them.

7.6. Emergency Power

The hotels should have adequate provision of emergency power in case of electrical outage to provide uninterrupted guest services in the hotel.

7.7. Emergency Manual

Hotels should have an emergency manual detailing all the operations and working in any event of various sorts of emergencies in the hotel.

7.8. Employee Photo Id

For added extra security of the guests in the hotels, all the employees should be provided with a photo ID which they should wear always during their work shift so that they can be easily identified by the guests.

7.9. In Room Safes

In room safes should be allocated in each guest room for the guests which can be easily operated using a secret password to keep and secure their valuables. Even the front desk of the hotels should have a safe deposit vault in which the guests can secure their valuables.

7.10. Guest Elevators

The guest elevators should be interfaced with the room electronic locking system where the room card key will lead the guests to the floor on which he is staying in the hotel.

For FEMALE / WOMEN GUESTS, the hotels adopt certain extra security measures which are as under

- 1) Mirrored walls of the guest room floor / corridor so that the female guest can actually watch who is walking behind her,
- 2) Well lit public areas like lobby, bars, swimming pool and parking place,
- 3) Valet parking services to avoid the need of a female guest to enter the parking area where doubtful and suspicious people can be present,
- 4) Assigning rooms closer to the elevators,
- 5) Assigning room to the female guest on a special executive floor with a security guard manned for 24 hours a day. Even up-gradation can be done for the female guest if room on the special executive floor is unavailable.

8. Crisis Management Plan

All the hotels should design and implement an emergency management plan to deal with any sort of emergency situation. According to the plan all the hotels should train their employees by mock drills in evacuations to help people in endangered situations. Even the hotels need to build their own strong in-house system to deal or prevent the emergency situation. There should be an emergency communication team within the hotel having staff from all the departments acting as emergency communication managers headed by a Nodal executive in charge of the emergency communication team.

The Nodal executive should have good coordination with the local administration and police authorities for quick and rapid deployment of the rapid action force during any sort of emergency.

9. Conclusion

All the hotels should adopt security and safety measures irrespective of their size or level of service, as security is considered to be an important prime concern for the guests who come to the hotel. Training personal safety and security measures is vital for hotel industry as it may boom or decline the industry as they are directly proportional to each other. The hotels should use technology as well they should train their employees to protect their guests in any sort of emergency. Safety and Security has become an important element of hospitality now a days as the guests have become more safety conscious. Also by the efficient use of safety and security measures, the hotels can attain their pre-determined objective of “GUEST SATISFACTION” when the guests feel that they are at home. The hotel can also build and maintain their rapport and can even maintain healthy customer relations if they provide world class security to the guests during their stay in the hotels. Lastly the hotel could collect more profits and improve the nation’s economy if they relocate their optimum safety and security measures for the well being of most important and their employees.

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